

THE PROCESS AND MECHANISM RESEARCH OF IN SITU DEPOSITED NANO-SiO₂ ON THE SURFACE OF JUTE FIBER

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ABSTRACT

Nano-SiO₂ particles were deposited on the surface of jute fibers by sol-gel method. Combined with single factor experiment, the effects of different reaction parameters (reaction time, TEOS dosage, reaction temperature and the ammonia concentration) on the morphology of nano-SiO₂ deposited on jute fiber surface were discussed. The results showed that with the increasing of TEOS dosage or ammonia concentration, the deposition amount and the size of nano-SiO₂ particles on the surface of jute fiber gradually increased. When the reaction temperature gradually increased, the deposition amount of nano-SiO₂ particles increased, yet the particle size of nano-SiO₂ decreased. When the reaction temperature was 80 °C, the deposition amount of nano-SiO₂ particles increased to 16.3wt%, while the particle size reduced to 20nm. With the increasing of reaction time, the deposition amount and the size of nano-SiO₂ particles increased, then the deposition amount and the particle size would not be varied when the reaction time exceeded 16h. At the same time, the acting mechanism between jute fibers and nano-SiO₂ was explored. TEOS on the surface of jute fibers reacted hydrolysis and condensation, and nano-SiO₂ cross-linked structure was obtained. Then the nano-SiO₂ cross-linked structure formed the physical or chemical bonding with the hydroxyl of jute fibers.

1 INTRODUCTION

Plant fibers were widely used as the reinforcement of thermoplastic composites, because of their abundant source, short growth period, light weight, high specific strength and friendly-environment [1]. However, the strong hydrophilic and flammability of plant fibers restricted their applications [2]. Plant fibers were usually treated with conventional physical and chemical modification treatments, such as alkali treatment, coupling treatment, grafting treatment and so on [3,4], which reduced the polarity of plant fibers to a certain extent [5,6], but the modification effects of plant fibers had not yet been brought into full play.

In recent years, some studies have shown that nano-particles could reduce the hydrophilic of plant fibers [7]. Plant fibers with porous surface provided favorable conditions for nucleation and growth of nano-particles [8, 9]. Polar hydroxyl of plant fibers could form chemical bonds or hydrogen bonds with inorganic nano-particles [10, 11], so as to effectively reduce hydrophilic of plant fibers. Sun et al. [12] reported that nano-TiO₂ particles were deposited on wood surface by hydrothermal method. Due to the hydrophobic nano-TiO₂ particles coated on wood surface, the polarity of wood was reduced. However, the report of nano-particles deposited on plant fiber surface was mainly concentrated in wood fiber, and there was few report about nano-particles deposited on linen fiber surface.

In this paper, nano-SiO₂ particles were deposited on the surface of jute fibers by sol-gel method, and the acting mechanism between jute fiber and nano-SiO₂ was explored. Besides, the effects of deposition process parameters on the morphology of nano-SiO₂ particles on the surface of jute fibers were analyzed.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

Jute fibers with diameter of 100 μ m were purchased from Jinling Wo International Trade Co. Ltd. Tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS) and ethanol were provided by Aladdin Shanghai Co. Ltd. Ammonia (NH₃, 25%) and sodium hydroxide were provided by Nanjing Co. Ltd.

2.2 Experimental methods

Firstly, jute fibers (0.02g) were treated with sodium hydroxide solution (8.0wt%, 100mL) at 25 °C for 120min, and then dried at 105 °C for 24h in a vacuum drying oven.

Then the treated jute fibers (0.02g) were soaked in the mixed solution A (6ml distilled water and 25ml ethanol solution) at 25 °C for 24h. In addition, 20mL ethanol and 3mL TEOS solution were fully mixed, then they were slowly added into the solution A, and the solution B was obtained. Then the ammonia solution (0.1mol/L, 3mL) was added to the solution B and kept stirred at 25 °C for 10h. Finally, the jute fibers were ultrasonically rinsed (200Hz, 25 °C) with distilled water for 10min, and dried at 80 °C for 24h in a vacuum drying oven.

2.3 Characterizations

The morphology of nano-SiO₂ particles on the surface of jute fibers was examined by SEM (Quanta 200, FEI). FTIR spectra of jute fibers were recorded by using FTIR (Nicolet Nexus 870).

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Infrared spectra

Fig. 1 Infrared spectra of pre-and post in situ deposited Nano-SiO₂ on the surface of jute fiber (a the untreated jute fiber, b the treated jute fiber)

The functional groups of jute fibers before and after the sol-gel treatment were examined by the infrared spectra and presented in Figure 1. The absorption band of -OH stretching of jute fibers occurred at 3410cm⁻¹. The peak at 2922cm⁻¹ was ascribable to -CH stretching in the methyl groups of jute fibers. Compared to the functional group of untreated jute fibers, the sol-gel treated jute fibers illustrated a band at 448cm⁻¹, which was attributed to Si-O-Si stretch vibration [13]. The peaks at 804cm⁻¹ and 1072cm⁻¹ were corresponding to Si-O-C stretch vibration and Si-O-C bending vibration,

which illuminated the hydroxyl groups of jute fibers combined with hydroxyl groups of nano-particles [14].

3.2 EDS

Fig. 2 Energy spectrum analysis of pre- and post in situ deposited Nano-SiO₂ on the surface of jute fiber (a the untreated jute fiber, b the treated jute fiber)

Figure 2 showed the EDS spectra of the untreated and treated samples. Co existing elements in the region were C and O, and these two elements were just the components of jute fiber. Compared between 2a and 2b, the content of O on the treated samples was more than the untreated samples. Besides, a significant Si peak appeared at about 1.6 Kev in the spectra of the treated sample, which suggested that SiO₂ was grown on the surface of jute fiber through sol-gel method.

3.3 Effect of process parameters on the microstructure of nano-SiO₂

(1) TEOS Dosages

When the TEOS dosage was varied from 1mL to 3, 5, 7mL respectively, the effect of TEOS dosage on the deposition amounts of nano-SiO₂ on the surface of jute fiber was as shown in Fig.3. It could be seen that with the increasing of TEOS dosage, the deposition amount of nano-SiO₂ on the surface of jute fiber increased gradually. When the TEOS dosage changed from 1mL to 3, 5, 7mL, the deposition amounts of nano-SiO₂ on jute fiber surface were 2.1%, 10.2%, 13.6%, 14.1% of 3a, 3b, 3c and 3d, respectively (Fig3, 4).

While the particle size of nano-SiO₂ on the surface of jute fiber increased firstly and then the particle size decreased with the increasing of TEOS dosage. When the TEOS dosage was 5mL, the particle size reached the maximum value of 200nm. This was because the high dosage of TEOS could promote the hydrolysis of TEOS, and the hydrolysis products of Si(OC₂H₅)_{4-x}OH_x increased, leading the nano-SiO₂ cross-linking network on the surface of jute fiber growth, thus the particle size of nano-SiO₂ increased. However, when TEOS dosage was more than 5mL, the nucleation rate of nano-SiO₂ on the surface of jute fiber increased quickly, so the particle size decreased. Besides, it could see clearly that nano-SiO₂ particles deposited on the surface of jute fiber were regular spherical particles

and preferentially nucleated in the micro pores of jute fibers. This was because there were lots of micropores on the surface of jute fiber, which could reduce the capacity for the nucleation of nano-SiO₂.

Fig.3 Surface morphologies of jute fiber under different TEOS dosages (3a 1mL; 3b 3mL; 3c 5mL; 3d 7mL)

Fig. 4 The deposition and particle size variation of nano-SiO₂ on the surface of jute fiber under different TEOS dosages

(2) Reaction Temperature

Fig.5 Surface morphologies of jute fiber under different reaction temperatures
(5a 20 °C; 5b 40 °C; 5c 60 °C; 5d 80 °C)

Fig. 6 The deposition and particle size variation of nano-SiO₂ on the surface of jute fiber under different reaction temperature

When the reaction temperature was varied from 20 °C to 40, 60, 80 °C respectively, the effect of reaction temperature on the deposition amount and the size of nano-SiO₂ on the surface of jute fiber was as shown in Fig.5. With the increasing of the reaction temperature, the deposition amount of nano-SiO₂ increased, yet the particle size decreased. When the reaction temperature was 80 °C, the deposition amount increased to 16.3%, while the particle size was reduced to 20nm (Fig. 6). If keep other variable parameters unchanged, only changing reaction temperature, the size distribution of nano-SiO₂ was narrow (Fig.5).

With the increasing of reaction temperature, the particle size decreased. This was because when the reaction temperature increased, the equilibrium solubility of nano-SiO₂ increased rapidly, and the growth period of nano-SiO₂ particles become shorter, thus the particle size became smaller. Besides, the higher reaction temperature made the volatilization rate of ethanol accelerated, which indirectly increased the concentration of precursor solution, so the nucleation of nano-SiO₂ increased, the size of nano-SiO₂ deposited on the surface of jute fiber decreased. Therefore, in order to obtain the small size of nano-SiO₂ particle on the surface of jute fiber, the reaction temperature was ought to increase.

(3) NH₄OH Concentration

NH₄OH concentration has a significant influence on morphology of nano-SiO₂ on the surface of jute fiber. When the ammonia concentration was varied from 0.8mol/L to 1.8, 2.8, 3.8mol/L respectively, the effect of reaction temperature on the deposition amount and the size of nano-SiO₂ on the surface of jute fiber was as shown in Fig.7, 8. When the ammonia concentration increased, the deposition amount of nano-SiO₂ particles gradually increased, and the particle size also become larger. Especially when the ammonia concentration exceeded 2.8mol/L, the nano-SiO₂ particles changed sharply bigger which almost closed to the micron level. At this time, the ammonia concentration was too high, causing the rate of TEOS condensation too fast, so the growth of nano-SiO₂ particles was not easy to control. It led to serious agglomeration of nano-SiO₂ and the particles could not be dispersed (Fig.7d).

Fig.7 Surface morphologies of jute fiber under different concentration of ammonia
(7a 0.8mol/L; 7b 1.8 mol/L; 7c 2.8 mol/L; 7d 3.8 mol/L)

Fig. 8 The deposition and particle size variation of nano-SiO₂ on the surface of jute fiber under different NH₄OH concentration

(4) Reaction Time

Fig.9 Surface morphologies of jute fiber under different reaction time
(9a 8h; 9b 16h; 9c 24h; 9d 32h)

Fig. 10 The deposition and particle size variation of nano-SiO₂ on the surface of jute fiber under different reaction time

When the reaction time was varied from 8h to 16, 24, 32h respectively, the effect of reaction time on the deposition amount on the surface of jute fiber was as shown in Fig 9, 10. The results showed the reaction time had a little effect on the deposition amount of nano-SiO₂. At the beginning during deposition (<16h), the amount of nano-SiO₂ increased rapidly with the increasing of reaction time. However, when the reaction time was more than 16h, the deposition amount of nano-SiO₂ almost unchanged. This was because when the reaction time was less than 16h, TEOS was not fully hydrolyzed. Therefore, with the extension of the reaction time, the hydrolysis rate of TEOS increased and the deposition increased. However, when the reaction time was more than 16h, TEOS had been completely hydrolyzed, the surface of jute fiber was covered by nanoparticles, and no surface active group of the jute fiber was exposed, so when the reaction time was more than 16h, the deposition amount of nano-SiO₂ on the surface of jute fiber would remain the same with the reaction time prolonged.

Besides, with the increasing of reaction time, the particle size of nano-SiO₂ on jute fiber surface increased, but the growth rate was small, indicating that the reaction time had little influence on the particle size.

3.4 Acting mechanism between jute fiber and nano-SiO₂

Based on the results mentions above, a schematic illustration of the in-situ deposition of nano-SiO₂ on jute fiber surface was proposed and shown in Fig.11. Jute fibers were impregnated in the distilled water and the water could flow into the internal along the micro-pore of jute fibers to some extent. At this time, TEOS solution was added and the hydrolytic reaction of TEOS occurred [15], obtaining the hydrolysate product of silanol (1). Due to the instability of the hydrolysate product of silanol, polycondensation reaction took place and nano-SiO₂ cross-linked structure was formed(2) (3). Some nano-SiO₂ cross-linked structure without nucleation directly reacted with the hydroxyl of jute fiber, forming Si-O-C chains (4) (6). Another nano-SiO₂ cross-linked structure integrated sphere nano-SiO₂ particles(5). Due to the presence of hydroxyl on the surface of nano-SiO₂, it can form the physical or chemical bonding with the jute fiber (7). As a result, nano-SiO₂ particles were deposited on the surface of jute fibers.

Fig. 11 The schematic illustration of in situ deposited Nano-SiO₂ on the surface of jute fiber

4 Conclusions

(1) Nano-SiO₂ particles were successfully deposited on the surface of jute fiber by ultrasonic sol-gel method and they were mainly deposited in the micro-pores of jute fibers. The shape of nano-SiO₂ was sphere and the minimum size was 20nm.

(2) With the increasing of TEOS concentration or ammonia content, the deposition amount of nano-SiO₂ and its size on the surface of jute fiber gradually increased. When the reaction temperature gradually increased, the deposition amount increased, yet the particle size decreased. Besides with the increasing of reaction time, the deposition amount of nano-SiO₂ and particle size increased, then the deposition amount of nano-SiO₂ and particle size would not be varied when the reaction time was more than 16h.

(3) The surface structure of jute fiber provided favorable conditions for nano-SiO₂ particle nucleation. TEOS on the surface of jute fiber reacted hydrolysis and condensation, obtaining nano-SiO₂ cross-linked structure and then forming the physical or chemical bonding with the surface hydroxyl of jute fiber.

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